

Enabling Plasticity in FPGA-based SNNs: an EEG Seizure Detection Study

Paola Busia^[0000-0002-1434-9858], Andrea Matticola^[0009-0003-3576-5038],
Luigi Raffo^[0000-0001-9683-009X], Paolo Meloni^[0000-0002-8106-4641], and
Gianluca Leone^[0000-0001-5265-0759]

DIEE Università degli Studi di Cagliari, Cagliari CA 09123, Italy
{paola.busia, paolo.meloni, gianluca.leone94}@unica.it

Abstract. Real-time classification or anomaly detection tasks on sensor data often represent a significant challenge, due to signal variability and noise levels corrupting the data in unpredictable ways. This issue is especially relevant in biomedical applications, where data acquisition is noticeably unbalanced, inter-person and inter-day signal variability is non-negligible, and data annotation is an extremely complex task to be completed by expert physicians. In this context, Spiking Neural Networks (SNNs) provide the interesting opportunity of mimicking the learning capabilities of the brain through different plasticity mechanisms, which allow an online refinement of the model’s parameters in an unsupervised fashion. This work aims at leveraging plasticity to adjust on the fly the classification performance of a lightweight SNN model, targeting biological signal monitoring in the wearable domain, by relying on a specialized low-power SNN accelerator enabling signal classification within a power envelope of 0.25 mW. The efficacy of the approach is evaluated on a seizure recognition problem based on the real-time processing of the electroencephalography (EEG) signal, where ensuring a good trade-off between anomaly detection and false-alarms minimization is paramount, and seizure occurrences vary significantly. The plasticity rule is executed on the host RISC-V processor integrated in the FPGA-based accelerator, enabling efficient and self-adaptive always-on monitoring with a negligible impact on the system’s power consumption.

Keywords: Plasticity · Spiking Neural Networks · FPGA · Low-power

1 Introduction

Spiking Neural Networks (SNNs) have recently emerged as third-generation neural networks, due to the inherent efficiency ensured by event-driven computations and binary data representation. Combined with the possibility of replacing resource-hungry multiplications with additions during real-time inference execution, these advantages make them especially promising as processing models for the wearable domain. Furthermore, their time-dependent evolution enables accounting for the context of previously processed data, which is especially interesting for sensor data processing.

To enable efficient exploitation of this sparse and event-driven computation, specialized neuromorphic architectures have been developed, also focusing on low-power solutions [18]. Some recent efforts have considered efficient FPGA-based implementations suitable for the ultra-low-power domain, leveraging the flexibility of reconfigurable logic to allocate different encoding schemes and focusing on low-end devices fostering wide accessibility [15, 19].

Nonetheless, the real-time processing of sensor data poses very specific challenges, connected to a significant variability of the acquired signals due to changing noise levels, sensor drift, etc, as can be observed in biomedical applications in terms of inter-session/inter-day variability. A promising approach to address this issue is to rely on online refinement techniques, enabling adaptivity to these changing conditions. A recently emerging line of research focuses on mimicking biologically inspired learning mechanisms in SNNs, through the definition of synaptic connections supporting plasticity as a weight modulation rule accounting for changes in conductivity caused by pre- and post-synaptic activity [16]. However, the integration of these mechanisms in devices at the wearable scale requires careful resource reuse.

With this objective, in this work, we start from the SYNtzulu [11] template for SNN acceleration on low-end FPGAs, integrating with minimal resource overhead the necessary logic to implement spike monitoring and online weight update. To minimize the resource usage, we exploit software/hardware interaction to access the hardware monitoring registers and compute weight update based on Short-Term-Plasticity (STP) on the host RISC-V processor.

The main contributions are listed in the following:

- we present an efficient neuromorphic system based on SYNtzulu [11], integrating support for online refinement through STP-based weight updates with negligible additional resource requirements;
- we demonstrate the feasibility of real-time weight update through efficient implementation on the RISC-V host processor in SYNtzulu, where STP execution does not impact the latency of signal classification;
- we validate the proposed STP-based update rule on a meaningful use-case, namely unobtrusive electroencephalography (EEG) monitoring for seizure detection, demonstrating a 70% reduction of the false alarms raised on the examined EEG records compared to the state-of-the-art static SNN model considered as baseline.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 summarizes the state of the art, Section 3 describes the implemented methodology, Section 4 presents the experimental results, and Section 5 discusses the comparison with the literature.

2 Related Work

Spike-Time-Dependent Plasticity (STDP) has been exploited in the literature to perform unsupervised training of SNN models by strengthening connections based on the causality between post- and pre-synaptic firing. An example is

represented by the ASIC proposed in [13] for the training of an MNIST classifier. Another typical learning mechanism observed in neuroscience is STP, which produces transient changes in the importance of synaptic connections as a consequence of the pre-synaptic activity [16]. Along with long-term potentiation/depression rules, these temporary changes in synaptic connectivity have been considered to enhance the adaptivity of SNN models to new data. A solution combining an STDP-based training stage with an online refinement based on STP has been considered in [17], demonstrating an improved robustness in noisy MNIST and EMNIST images classification thanks to online STP. As another example, fatiguing STDP has been introduced in [16] as a learning rule combining both STDP and STP effects to improve SNN learning on weather correlations.

In this work, we explore the impact of STP as an online refinement mechanism to increase the robustness of biological sensor data classification, starting from a model pre-trained in a supervised fashion. A significant reference was provided by [4], where STP was exploited to enable continuous noise filtering in action potential and bursts detection from micro-electrode array (MEA) acquisition. Compared to the STP implementation exploited in [4], we refined the weight update rule to enable a more gradual recovery of the weight module. Furthermore, focusing on the near-sensor domain as a deployment target, we optimized the STP rule implementation to be efficiently integrated in an ultra-low-power FPGA-based SNN accelerator and executed on the simple host RISC-V processor. This solution represents an innovation compared to the FPGA-based alternatives in the literature supporting plasticity mechanisms, mostly oriented to high performance over the strict energy efficiency constraints required for wearable deployment [24, 23, 1]. On the contrary, the interesting architectural solution proposed in [4] is customized on a fixed two-neuron network topology. A detailed quantitative comparison is discussed in Section 5.

Due to the challenges connected to seizure data acquisition and annotation, as well as to seizure occurrence variability, EEG seizure detection represents a relevant use case to assess the advantages of online model refinement through plasticity. For this reason, autoencoder solutions for unsupervised training [26, 25, 5] and support for continual learning buffering new seizure events along with previous training samples [20] have been proposed.

In this context, a detector leveraging the plasticity of its synaptic connections to adapt to signal corruption, due to noise or artifacts, represents a promising opportunity for long-term monitoring, combined with the efficiency of sparse and binary SNN inference, which have been recently explored as detection models [3, 27, 12, 6]. To the best of our knowledge, the use of plasticity as an online refinement mechanism in this context was only previously considered in [27], integrating an STDP-based online learning module. In this work, we explore a different plasticity mechanism, STP, and we discuss its impact on the real-time seizure detection performance, considering it as an always-on weight update rule. Finally, compared to the FPGA implementation proposed in [27], we demonstrate an improved energy efficiency in real-time execution.

3 Method

This section describes the details of the proposed SNN model, the implemented STP rule, the hardware target, and the EEG seizure detection use-case.

3.1 Lightweight SNN classifier.

The proposed system integrates a state-of-the-art lightweight SNN model [2], suitable to reach an acceptable EEG classification performance with a power envelope compatible with wearable deployment. The input encoding follows the approach exploited in [2], where the amplitude of the signal sampled at time t on each of the acquisition channels is encoded into 16 one-hot amplitude levels, selected based on the typical amplitude observed in the training records.

The topology of the model is depicted in Fig. 1. It exploits two layers of Leaky-Integrate-and-Fire (LIF) neurons: the first layer is composed of 8 neurons, each integrating through time the input signal information received from 64 input synapses and combined through a 64×8 Dense layer; the output layer is fully connected to the previous stage and includes a single neuron, whose output rate is compared to a pre-trained discrimination threshold th_{class} to obtain the final classification into two different classes, *non-seizure* or *seizure*.

The LIF mechanism considered for the implementation is recalled in the following. The neuron membrane voltage stores the history of the previously processed input spikes, evolving based on Equation 1.

$$\tilde{v}(t+1) = \alpha \cdot v(t) + \sum w \cdot s_{in}(t+1) \quad (1)$$

where $s_{in}(t+1)$ is the input train of spikes, w are the synaptic weights assigned to the input connections, and α is a decay factor.

$$s_{out}(t+1) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \tilde{v}(t+1) \geq \theta \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$v(t+1) = \begin{cases} \tilde{v}(t+1), & \text{if } \tilde{v}(t+1) < \theta \\ \tilde{v}(t+1) - \theta, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

When the membrane voltage reaches a threshold value θ , the neuron produces an output spike s_{out} , according to Equation 2. As a consequence, the membrane voltage is reset by subtracting the threshold value, as reported in Equation 3.

The model was implemented exploiting the SnnTorch library [7], enabling LIF evolution modeling and supervised training with backpropagation through time on the PyTorch framework. Training execution was performed on Google Colaboratory.

Fig. 1: Topology of the considered SNN model.

3.2 Short-Term Plasticity.

STP models the effects of synaptic fatigue, due to a reduced concentration of the neurotransmitter in the pre-synaptic terminal, thus temporarily decreasing the weight of the connection with each spike transmitted [16].

Taking inspiration from [4], in this work, we focus on STP as a filtering mechanism for frequent synaptic activity, interpreted as noise and thus determining temporary synaptic depression. We focus on the synapses connecting to the output neuron, highlighted in Fig. 1, and particularly on those having learned a positive weight during the supervised training, whose activity contributes positively to the output rate of the classification neuron (i.e., seizure prediction). To define the frequency of the synaptic activity, we trace the number of spikes s_{io} transmitted along the plastic synapse within a rate observation window of T time steps. As reported in Equation 4, this rate r_{io} is multiplied by the connection weight w_{io} to compute the input current transmitted to the output neuron along that connection during the last T steps.

$$c_i(n) = w_{io}(n) \cdot \sum_{t=0}^T s_{io}(t) = w_{io}(n) \cdot r_{io}(n) \quad (4)$$

To evaluate the transient modification, the current c_i is compared to a typical current value C_i , expected on each connection based on the training data available for the normal class. The weight update rule is reported in Equation 5, where D_i and P_i are synaptic-specific parameters, selected based on the training data to ensure that no relevant modification would be applied to the weights in a typical normal window.

$$w_{io}(n+1) = \begin{cases} w_{io}(n) - D_i \cdot r_{io}(n), & \text{if } c_i(n) > C_i \\ w_{io}(n) + P_i \cdot (1 - r_{io}(n)), & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The description of the selection process for the C_i , P_i , and D_i parameters in the seizure classification use-case is reported in Section 3.4.

As can be observed, after every evaluation window, the plastic weights are either increased or decreased, based on the observed input rate. This solution also enables a gradual potentiation of synaptic connections that exhibit reduced activity, compared to the synaptic behavior proposed in [4], where the effect of depression is reset immediately in the absence of spikes.

Finally, as the system aims at anomaly detection, we expect the neurons reacting to anomaly-specific patterns to increase their activity when the anomaly occurs. Since this increased activity should not be treated as noise, a stop criterion is needed for the STP weight updates. To this aim, we exploit the classification threshold applied to the output rate for anomaly recognition, th_{class} , assuming that the target is only reached in the presence of a seizure. To account for the impact of STP on the instantaneous output rate of the classification neuron, th_{class} is also updated with the same frequency as the connection weights, according to Equation 6.

$$th_{class} = th_{class} \cdot (0.35 + 0.65 \cdot \frac{\sum_{i=0}^C w_{io}(n+1)}{\sum_{i=0}^C w_{io}(n)}) \quad (6)$$

The fundamental steps of the implemented STP update rule are summarized in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1: Implemented STP Update Rule

Input: *Synaptic Weights, Classification Threshold, Input Spike Rate, Output Spike Rate*

Result: *Updated Weights w , Updated Threshold th_{class}*

```

1  $w$  = Pretrained Synaptic Weights;
2  $th_{class}$  = Pretrained Classification Threshold;
3 Eval sum of Weights at previous step,  $S_{n-1}$ ;
4 while Output Spike Rate <  $th_{class}$  do
5   if  $w_i(n-1) > 0$  then
6     Evaluate Input Current  $c_i$ ;
7     if  $c_i > C_i$  then
8        $\lfloor$  Apply Weight Depression  $w_i(n)$ ;
9     else
10     $\lfloor$  Apply Weight Potentiation  $w_i(n)$ ;
11   Eval sum of Weights at current step,  $S_n$ ;
12   Update Classification Threshold;

```

Fig. 2: Target hardware architecture and training/detection cycle overview.

3.3 Target Hardware.

The algorithm has been deployed on SYNtzulu [11], an open-source¹ digital neuromorphic architecture optimized for low-cost and low-power FPGAs, such as the Lattice iCE40UP5K. SYNtzulu’s architecture includes:

- A dual-core sparsity-aware accelerator of spiking dense layers, in charge of computing neuron input currents due to spike activity and of evaluating neuron dynamics in the SNN, updating the voltages, and applying thresholds. The accelerator goes idle as soon as all spikes are processed, thus maximizing energy efficiency;
- A compact bit-serial RISC-V core², responsible for managing input/output data flows, standby mode, and system initialization, such as model loading, at startup;
- Configurable encoding slot, to convert input samples into spikes;
- Configurable decoding slot, to interpret the classification results, e.g., to compute output spike rates.

In this work, we start from the implementation described in [2], already customized to implement the encoding and decoding algorithms of the considered use case. However, we regularly exploit the idle periods in the system, determined by the sparsity of spikes in the application at hand, to compute the STP learning mechanism in real time, leveraging the tiny RISC-V core already included in the architecture. The execution of the STP algorithm requires monitoring the neurons’ firing rates and accessing the weight memory. Thus, we extended the

¹ <https://github.com/gianlucaleone/SYNtzulu>

² <https://github.com/olofk/serv/>

hardware design, including eight 12-bit counters accessible by the microprocessor, one for each neuron of the first layer of the SNN model, and we granted the microprocessor write access to the weight memory.

The choice of deploying the plasticity task on the RISC-V processor is motivated by the need to keep the implementation as lightweight as possible, while ensuring significant flexibility thanks to software-based plasticity definition. As demonstrated by the results observed on the target use-case, weight updates can be evaluated on windows of signal, representing a low-frequency task compared to inference operations. Therefore, hardware acceleration is not strictly necessary, while requiring additional hardware resources, e.g., to support division, as well as additional design effort for any update on the considered plasticity rule. Furthermore, software-based support allows for fully leveraging the computing power of the RISC-V core, already available in the system, while retaining higher precision in intermediate weights representation (32-bit fixed point) than exploited in hardware (8-bit fixed point), thus allowing for accurate and gradual updates.

Fig. 2 depicts the interaction between the RISC-V core and the hardware accelerator during STP execution, as well as an illustrative time diagram of the training/detection cycle.

3.4 EEG Seizure detection use-case.

For the considered seizure detection use case, we referenced the open-source CHB-MIT Scalp EEG dataset [21, 9], curated by the Children’s Hospital Boston and the Massachusetts Institute of Technology. The dataset includes a list of scalp EEG records from 23 epileptic patients, acquired with a 256 Hz sampling frequency and reporting a precise annotation of the onset of the occurred seizure events. Based on a typical unobtrusive behind-the-ear acquisition setup for continuous monitoring in everyday life with a wearable system [22, 8], we limit the analysis to the signal acquired with the four temporal channels, namely F7-T7, T7-P7, F8-T8, T8-P8, according to the 10-20 international system. The encoding of these signals into 16 one-hot amplitude levels produces the 64 trains of spikes provided as input to the network in Fig. 1.

As seizure detection is commonly addressed as a patient-specific problem [10], we considered a subset of 6 patients and performed a different supervised training for each one. The training and validation set included all but the last seizure records available for the subject, whereas the last seizure record was left out to be included in the test set. To further assess the stability and robustness of the seizure detection, we also included in the test set consecutive non-seizure records, accounting for 5 hours of test data per patient on average. This approach ensures a clear separation between the training and test sets, allowing us to evaluate the reliability of raised alarms, as well as the impact of event variability with time for the same subject, and the advantage of an online refinement approach.

The synaptic-specific parameters exploited in the STP update rule, i.e., C_i , D_i , and P_i , were selected with a patient-specific approach, based on the available training examples for the non-seizure data. In detail, the typical current C_i was

defined according to Equation 4, considering the average firing rate observed on the corresponding synapse when processing all the training non-seizure windows learned correctly, i.e., where the output firing rate of the trained model was under 0.05, compared to a training target of 0.03. Finally, the parameters P_i and D_i were selected to ensure that, when r_{io} equals the typical non-seizure rate, Equation 5 does not produce any changes in the weight value. The values obtained for the considered subjects are reported in Table 1, referring to only the synaptic connections having learned a positive weight during supervised training. The code for model training and STP-based inference has been released as open source³.

Table 1: STP parameters obtained from training data for the considered subjects. The value of D_i is obtained based on a P_i set to 3.13e-07.

Channel	<i>chb01</i>		<i>chb02</i>		<i>chb03</i>		<i>chb05</i>		<i>chb07</i>		<i>chb08</i>	
	D_i e-07	C_i e-02										
1	-	-	-	-	684.7	0.7	-	-	-	-	1724.4	0.3
2	9.01	9.1	1045	0.3	54.07	4	-	-	15.1	4.1	-	-
3	6.64	10.3	1024	0.2	-	-	-	-	129.4	1.1	1544	0.2
4	-	-	28.6	4.2	-	-	183.2	0.7	54.88	2	-	-
5	-	-	18.9	5.2	39.5	3.5	3.4	16.4	-	-	1465	0.3
6	7.19	5.7	-	-	10.19	8.3	-	-	-	-	1725	0.2
7	16.4	3.9	36.4	2.1	-	-	-	-	111.3	0.8	567.6	0.5
8	4.77	13.6	-	-	-	-	646.1	0.4	-	-	1288	0.2

4 Experimental Results

This section summarizes the assessment of STP impact on real-time classification and of the achievable on-hardware efficiency.

4.1 Impact on real-time classification performance

The classification performance is analyzed at the segment level and event level. We consider a segment a window of $T = 4096$ samples, corresponding to 16 seconds of data, which are processed to compute the output rate and evaluate the classification output. A new classification is produced for each new sample; therefore, the number of evaluated segments matches the number of acquired samples. Event-level metrics refer to the percentage of seizure occurrences detected and to the number of false-positives-per-hour (FP/h) raised, where we consider as a single FP event a sequence of FPs with less than 10 seconds distance, in alignment with [2]. The reported classification results consider a 20-second pre-ictal tolerance and a 15-minute post-ictal tolerance.

As a baseline for the evaluation of the efficacy of STP, we first collected the classification performance of the static model obtained with supervised training,

³ <https://github.com/andem25/STPSNN>

Table 2: Test classification performance with static and STP inference.

Subject	[2] Static (without STP)						STP					
	Segment-level				Event-level		Segment-level				Event-level	
	Acc	Sens	Spec	AUC	Sens	FP/h	Acc	Sens	Spec	AUC	Sens	FP/h
chb01	99.9%	84.6%	99.99%	97.5%	100%	0.2	99.9%	82.3%	100%	96.5%	100%	0
chb02	99.7%	31.6%	99.7%	99.1%	100%	1.17	99.6%	100%	99.6%	99.8%	100%	0.3
chb03	99.9%	60.9%	100%	99.8%	100%	0	99.9%	70.4%	100%	99.8%	100%	0
chb05	99.8%	66.1%	100%	99.2%	100%	0	99.5%	20.1%	100%	98.4%	100%	0
chb07	99.8%	67.4%	100%	99.8%	100%	0	99.9%	82%	100%	98.6%	100%	0
chb08	99.1%	44.8%	99.9%	91.2%	100%	0.4	99.2%	45.2%	100%	95.1%	100%	0
Average	99.7%	59.9%	99.9%	97.8%	100%	0.2	99.7%	56.2%	99.9%	98%	100%	0.06

exploiting fixed-weighted synaptic connections to the output neuron [2]. The classification threshold for each subject was selected based on the output rate observed on training seizure segments, specifically as the minimum between mode and median, to enable event-level detection. The results are reported in the left half of Table 2. As can be observed, the model enables the detection of all the examined seizure events, reaching an accuracy of over 99% on the data from all considered subjects. Nonetheless, the tests on patients *chb01*, *chb02* and *chb08* show up to 1.17 FP/h are raised, which may represent an issue for the practical use of the monitoring device.

The same set of tests was repeated after enabling the online update of synaptic weights and classification threshold based on the STP rule described in Section 3.2. The results are reported in the right half of Table 2. The most noticeable advantage is the 70% reduction on average of the FP/h obtained on the whole test duration, compared to the static baseline model in [2], up to 0.06 FP/h. This result derives from an improved segment-level specificity in patients *chb01* and *chb08*, and a reduction of the FP events in patient *chb02*. This latter test is especially useful to highlight the advantages of the approach. Fig. 3 shows the output rate obtained with static (Fig. 3a) and STP inference (Fig. 3b). At the beginning of the test, the spike patterns excited by the static model cause the output rate to grow and reach the seizure threshold, raising FPs around 2 hours before the seizure onset. Synaptic weight plasticity enables us to distinguish these temporary patterns from actual seizure occurrence, thus removing these FPs, while gradual synaptic potentiation allows the seizure neurons to recover their importance and enables seizure detection with an improved segment-level sensitivity. Furthermore, the false alarms raised during STP inference are raised significantly closer to the seizure event, only 13 minutes before.

From a general perspective, the specificity improvement does not compromise sensitivity, which is increased in subjects *chb02*, *chb03*, *chb07*, and *chb08*. The only test where STP inference did not provide any advantages, while reducing both the accuracy and segment-level sensitivity of the classification, is the one on subject *chb05*. Nonetheless, despite a reduced efficacy on this subject’s data, STP does not compromise the event-level seizure detection, preserving 100% of event-level seizure detection, and does not introduce any false alarms, demonstrating overall reliability.

(a) Static baseline model.

(b) STP.

Fig. 3: Output firing rate and classification output with and without STP on test data from subject chb02.

Fig. 4: Weight and classification threshold value over time during STP inference based on floating-point offline simulation and fixed-point execution on hardware.

4.2 Weight quantization and integer STP rule implementation.

To enable efficient inference on the hardware accelerator integrated in SYNTzulu, all synaptic weights were quantized to 8-bit precision. Furthermore, as the targeted RISC-V core only supports integer operations, all STP update rules were implemented with fixed-point integer arithmetic.

To demonstrate the precision of the fixed-point approximation of the STP rule, an example of weight update behavior for one of the seizure weights is reported in the top plot of Fig. 4, which refers to the first 2 hours of the test in Fig. 3. To retain sufficient precision, 32-bit fixed-point representation was exploited on the RISC-V processor: the updated weight value is stored until the next iteration for the evaluation of the next STP iteration, while a truncated 8-bit precision weight is offloaded to the local memory on the accelerator. As can be noticed, with this solution, the fixed-point implementation exploited on the RISC-V enables a precise approximation of the corresponding floating-point value, observed in the PyTorch-based simulated behavior, ensuring an accurate update of the weights based on the rule in Equation 5.

Fig. 4 also reports in the bottom plot the history of the classification threshold value obtained with the fixed-point implementation. In this case, the value is only stored in software with 32-bit precision, and the division in Equation 6 is implemented with the restoring division algorithm. The plot shows a limited approximation error introduced by the fixed-point arithmetic in the system for the instantaneous classification threshold evaluation. Finally, the comparison with the full-precision classification results demonstrates a negligible impact on the system’s accuracy.

4.3 Real-time on-hardware efficiency.

Real-time classification on SYNTzulu performs as in [2], since the SNN topology and the target hardware hyperparameters (such as the clock frequency and the number of parallel cores) have not been changed. A new inference is executed at every sample time by computing the evolution of the neuron state depending on the new spike activity. Inference computation requires 556 operations (OPS), however, due to an average sparsity of 82.8%, the typical workload running on the target hardware is 96 OPS. At 24 MHz working frequency, the average required inference time is 0.5 μ s. Core power consumption during inference execution was directly measured with a Digital Analog Discovery 2 oscilloscope and a $3.3 \pm 0.033 \Omega$ shunt resistor, resulting in 9.1 mW on average. The required energy per inference is therefore limited to 4.55 nJ. As soon as inference is completed, idle mode is activated; therefore, average power consumption over a sampling period is almost equal to idle power consumption, 0.25 mW, with a negligible impact resulting from STP execution, given the considered update frequency.

The execution of the STP algorithm on the RISC-V, performed once every 4096 samples (i.e., every 16 seconds), requires 4.23 ms, which exceeds the 3.9 ms sample period at 256 Hz. To address this, we split its computation across two sample times. Specifically, when a new sample arrives, the timer interrupt service

routine is triggered, and the new weights computation is temporarily paused. The computation is then completed as soon as the core finishes its housekeeping tasks, effectively applying the weights update one sample period later, as shown in the training/detection cycle at the bottom of Fig. 2. As previously mentioned, the update happens during the idle cycles deriving from SNN sparsity, thus it has no impact on the real-time performance of the classification and a negligible impact on the energy dissipation.

The additional logic required to support STP execution is minimal, i.e., 258 Logic Cells (LCs), 7.9% more than the baseline design in [2], whereas the utilization of other FPGA resources remains unchanged. The overall hardware requirements of the design are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Hardware Resources on Lattice ICE40UP5K

LC	DSP	BRAM [4 Kb]	SPRAM [256 Kb]	Frequency [MHz]
3529 (66%)	2 (25%)	14 (46%)	4 (100%)	24

5 Discussion

In this section, we evaluate the efficiency of the proposed neuromorphic system against relevant alternatives from the state of the art supporting plasticity mechanisms and implemented on an FPGA. Table 4 lists recent relevant works on this subject. As can be noticed, plasticity integration in neuromorphic FPGA processors has been considered with different objectives, ranging from brain activity simulation to unsupervised training for digit recognition. Based on the targeted use case, hardware design favors a different trade-off between performance maximization and power consumption minimization.

Starting from the work of [24], the proposed BiCoSS System-on-Chip (SOC) was developed as a large-scale cognitive supercomputing system for the real-time emulation of over 4 million neurons supporting STDP plasticity, thanks to the integration of up to 35 Intel EP4CE115 FPGAs, having an average power consumption of 10 W. On a smaller scale, in [1] the authors propose a system emulating context-dependent learning through STDP, exploiting over 34,000 LUTs. Support for plasticity has also been implemented as a solution for on-chip training targeting typical neuromorphic benchmarks, such as MNIST digit recognition [23], reporting 4 W power consumption. However, these solutions can not be easily adapted to the tight resource and power budgets typical of near-sensor processing at the wearable scale, as they generally dedicate different hardware structures for different sub-tasks in the system to increase parallelism.

On the contrary, this work aims at enabling the online model refinement capabilities offered by synaptic plasticity while fully exploiting the inherent efficiency of SNNs on low-end and low-power devices, such as the Lattice iCE40UP5K

Table 4: Comparison to state-of-the-art hardware implementation of online learning for SNNs.

Work	Use-case	Online Learning	Hardware	Frequency	Power	Energy
[24]	cerebellar motor learning	STDP	BiCoSS on Intel EP4CE115	N.R.	10 W	N.R.
[1]	context-dependent learning	STDP	Xilinx Kintex-7 XC7kt160t	143 MHz	1.91 W	N.R.
[23]	MNIST	STDP	Xilinx ZC706	125 MHz	4.4 W	N.R.
[4]	MEA spike detection	STP	Xilinx Kria KR260	585 MHz	0.36 W	N.R.
[14]	speech recognition	STDP	Xilinx ZC706	100 MHz	195 mW*	N.R.
[27]	EEG seizure	STDP	Xilinx ZCU102	100 MHz	-	3.73 μ J/class
this work	EEG seizure	STP	Lattice iCE40UP5K	24 MHz	9.1 mW	4.55 nJ/class

* Do not account for static power and ARM microprocessor power

Table 5: Comparison to state-of-the-art SNNs for seizure detection on the CHB-MIT dataset.

Model	Channels	Acc	Sens	Spec	OPS	Memory
[3]	22	97.1%	94.9%	99.3%	0.32 M	9.9 kB
[27]	23	98%	93.8%	98.64%	N.R.*	N.R.
[12]	2	93.3%	90.4%	96.7%	N.R.	2.4 kB
[6]	2	N.R.	78.7%	76.9%	57 k**	69 kB***
this work	4	99.7%	56.2%	99.9%	529	529 B

* Not Reported; ** Accounting for observed sparsity; *** Estimated from the paper.

FPGA. This is achieved through careful resource reuse on SYNtzu’s lightweight architecture, whose advantages are preserved by deploying the weight and classification threshold update task on the host RISC-V processor. Even compared to the works in the last half of the Table, reporting <1 W average power consumption for speech recognition [14] and real-time action potential and bursts detection [4] through STDP and STP, our work demonstrates the highest energy efficiency. Our approach shows a $20\times$ reduction in power consumption, despite Lattice iCE40UP5K being implemented on 40 nm technology node, while [14] and [4] target 24 and 16 nm chips, respectively. Nonetheless, a considerable portion of power is not accounted for in [14], such as the static power of the FPGA and the overall power of the host ARM Cortex-A9 MPCore microprocessor used for input/output management. Moreover, the SNN accelerator in [4] is a custom implementation tailored to a two-neuron topology. In contrast, our solution accounts for both static and host processor power, while our processor–accelerator co-working strategy can be applied to a wide range of network topologies by simply reconfiguring the accelerator and reprogramming the firmware component. Finally, with respect to [27], which is the only other architecture evaluated on EEG seizure detection, our work shows lower classification energy by almost 3 orders of magnitude. [27] instantiates multiple engines for two-level detection and online learning, thus uses a higher number of resources and requires a bigger FPGA.

To provide a clear context for the evaluation of the performance achieved in the EEG seizure detection use-case, we summarize in Table 5 the state of the art for SNN-based solutions on the CHB-MIT dataset. Among the listed works, only [27] refers to online learning support. As anticipated, the network topology considered as baseline demonstrated competitive seizure detection performance [2], and the results in the previous section highlight the impact of online refinement through STP in false alarms reduction. Despite a reduced segment-level sensitivity, the proposed system ensures the detection of all the examined seizure events. Although referring to different test approaches and data subsets, the performance metrics reported in Table 5 show how the STP-version of the model, exploiting dynamically adapting synapses, reaches classification metrics comparable to the alternatives compatible with unobtrusive acquisition setups [6, 12] and those exploiting full-montage setups [3, 27]. The considered use case thus provides a meaningful benchmark for the efficiency of the proposed system.

6 Conclusions

In this work, we presented the efficient integration of plasticity support on SYNtzulu’s architectural template, focusing on minimal resource overhead. Exploiting hardware/software interactions, we deploy the STP update rule on the host RISC-V processor, enabling online access to the local weight memory and to the newly introduced spike rate monitoring logic. The evaluation of the seizure detection use-case demonstrates an energy efficiency $20\times$ higher than the state-of-the-art alternative reporting the lowest power consumption among FPGA-based plasticity-supporting architectures. Furthermore, the classification performance assessment demonstrates the advantages of online STP in reducing the false-alarm rate of the static state-of-the-art SNN considered as baseline. These results provide a first validation of the efficacy of the proposed system. As future developments, we mean to further assess the impact of online plasticity by exploring additional use-cases, connected to real-time biological signal processing, and learning mechanisms, contributing to solving the issues connected to signal variability in sensor data processing. This further assessment aims at evaluating different accuracy and latency constraints, resulting in the definition of different network topologies, representing an additional benchmark for the proposed architecture.

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